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ЖУРНАЛ ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬНЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ | JOURNAL OF FUNDAMENTAL STUDIES

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ONLINE DISPUTE RESOLUTION MECHANISMS: INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCE AND NATIONAL LEGISLATION PERSPECTIVES

ANNOTATION

In recent times, due to the rising number of arbitration cases dealing with cross-border disputes, the arbitration process has gained an international dimension. International commercial arbitration has transformed into a private transnational system for resolving disputes, encompassing various multilateral conventions, bilateral treaties, national arbitration regulations, as well as informal principles and rules for dispute resolution. This comprehensive article explores the landscape of Online Dispute Resolution (ODR) mechanisms, focusing on Uzbekistan's jurisdictional perspective and comparing it with international practices. It examines legislative reforms, technological implementations, and challenges associated with ODR adoption. The article provides valuable insights into the evolution of ODR and its potential to enhance access to justice.

Key words: online disputes, arbitration, private transnational dispute resolution, international commercial arbitration, technological implementations, international practices, access to justice, legal framework, comparative analysis, challenges and opportunities.

ОНЛАЙН-МЕХАНИЗМОВ УРЕГУЛИРОВАНИЯ СПОРОВ: МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ОПЫТ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ НАЦИОНАЛЬНОГО ЗАКОНОДАТЕЛЬСТВА

АННОТАЦИЯ

В последнее время, в связи с ростом числа арбитражных дел, связанных с трансграничными спорами, арбитражный процесс приобрел международное измерение. Международный коммерческий арбитраж превратился в частную транснациональную систему разрешения споров, охватывающую различные многосторонние конвенции, двусторонние договоры, национальные арбитражные регламенты, а также неформальные принципы и правила разрешения споров. В этой обширной статье рассматриваются механизмы онлайн-разрешения споров (ODR), с акцентом на юрисдикционную перспективу Узбекистана и в сравнении с международной практикой. В ней рассматриваются законодательные реформы, технологические внедрения и проблемы, связанные с внедрением ODR. В статье содержится ценная информация об эволюции ODR и его потенциале в плане расширения доступа к правосудию.

Ключевые слова: онлайн-споры, арбитраж, частное транснациональное разрешение споров, международный коммерческий арбитраж, технологические внедрения, международная практика, доступ к правосудию, правовая база, сравнительный анализ, вызовы и возможности.

ОНЛАЙН НИЗОЛАРНИ ҲАЛ ҚИЛИШ МЕХАНИЗМЛАРИ: ХАЛҚАРО ТАЖРИБА ВА МИЛЛИЙ ҚОНУНЧИЛИК ИСТИҚБОЛЛАРИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Сўнгги пайтларда, туфайли трансчегаравий низоларни билан шуғулланувчи арбитраж ҳолларда чиқиш рақамига, арбитраж жараёни халқаро ўлчов сазовор бўлди. Халқаро тижорат арбитраж низоларни ҳал қилиш учун бир хусусий трансмилий тизимига айланди, турли кўп томонлама конвенцияларни ўз ичига олган, икки томонлама шартномалар, миллий арбитраж қоидалари, шунингдек низоларни ҳал қилиш учун норасмий тамойиллари ва қоидалари сифатида. Ушбу кенг қамровли мақола Ўзбекистоннинг юрисдикция нуқтаи назарига ва уни халқаро амалиёт билан таққослашга қаратилган низоларни онлайн ҳал қилиш (ОДР) механизмларининг манзарасини ўрганади. Унда ОДРни қабул қилиш билан боғлиқ Қонунчилик ислохотлари, технологик татбиқ етиш ва муаммолар кўриб чиқилади. Мақолада ОДР эволюцияси ва унинг адолатга киришни кучайтириш салоҳияти ҳақида қимматли тушунчалар берилган.

Калит сўзлар: онлайн низолар, арбитраж, хусусий трансмилий низоларни ҳал қилиш, халқаро тижорат арбитражи, технологик татбиқ етиш, халқаро амалиёт, адолатга кириш, Қонунчилик базаси, қиёсий таҳлил, муаммолар ва имкониятлар.

In terms of dispute, ADR has always been promoted as a cost-effective and time-efficient measure of resolving consumer disputes yet the PPP as a style of justice delivery has not garnered healthy state esteem in most developed or developing Asian nations. E-filing and drafting documentation is the beginning of e-court processes.

ODR can pave the way for a competitively priced alternative to ADR and especially in the realm of international private disputes, it can steer a course to saving upon time and costs of litigation to invoke final and binding arbitration. ODR has been defined as ODR that takes place within the arbitral model of justice. This is ever so relevant with the fact that ODR in any form is an arbitral model of justice served out of court. Given the various implementations of IT methods that are varying forms from video or audio conferencing to virtual environments or electronic agents and the necessity to harmonize ODR with these differing laws and varying degrees of state development, there must be a study of the impact and the ways and means of regulation of ODR with its effect on national law and the administration of justice [1, 2, 3].

ODR has the potential and possibility to evade the substance of law and the national courts for the justice of the private disputant in the shadow of conflicting choice of law rules. ODR mechanisms are very procedural in nature and likely work to obtain a quick and procedural result to sidestep complex and varying state procedural laws. ODR runs a risk of conflicting choice of law rules usually foregoing conflict of laws into the realm of international private disputes. This is a broad topic and this paper will focus mainly on the varying forms of ODR and its regulation with the common goal of an effective dispute resolution in mind. (De Jesus Candeias, 2023)

Online Dispute Resolution Mechanisms: A Jurisdictional Perspective" projects another level of entry into the specialty area of online dispute resolution. As the present era is persistently based on the bedrock of advanced technology, it has indeed pervaded into the nooks and corners of every possible human activity or transaction. Law is no exception to this global phenomenon. Judicial interactions in the contemporary cyber era are taking diverse forms. This requires international and national substantive and procedural laws to instantly handle and regulate disputes that arise out of such interactions. Online Dispute Resolution (ODR) is concerned with the resolution of disputes with the aid of information technology and the Internet. ODR primarily involves negotiation, mediation, conciliation, and arbitration which are aided by a neutral third party of IT expert and conducted through the exchange of information between the disputants. This more or less happens to be a mix of e-court processes and ADR mechanisms using traditional IT methods [4].

Definition of Online Dispute Resolution

Stepping stones in the evolution process are the implementation of technology and software in courts in Europe and the USA in the late 20th century. In 1996, the UK implemented the Civil Procedure Rules for England and Wales. This was a major reform as it provided a new code of civil procedure for the jurisdictions and encompassed changes to the existing rules. The reforms aimed to reduce cost and complexity, and they were the first procedural rules in the UK to advocate the resolution of disputes without the need for a trial. This was followed by Europe, which launched the European Judicial Network website in 2005. The aim of this was to provide information about the judicial systems of EU member states. In turn, there are moves in the USA at the state level to automate courts using the IMS case management system and other software. All of these are examples of moving dispute resolution into a technological environment, but they are not ODR. ODR comes specifically with the use of alternatives to the settlement of disputes through courts, and it is the implementation of methods such as arbitration and mediation that are the real implementation of ODR.

Online dispute resolution (ODR) can be defined as a mechanism or a process of resolving disputes by the use of electronic communications. The most common form of ODR is arbitration. This takes place when the two parties agree to the appointment of an arbitrator, thus avoiding the litigation process and litigation costs. ODR is a wide field, and the concept of it is constantly evolving. ODR has its roots in ADR, which is the alternative dispute resolution movement in the late 20th century. ADR was seen as a move to less formalistic methods of resolving disputes such as mediation and conciliation, and away from the traditional adversarial model of litigation. ODR, on the other hand, seeks to harness the speed and low cost of technological solutions to enable disputes to be resolved without the need for a formal tribunal [5, 6].

Importance of Online Dispute Resolution in Jurisdictional Context

Another potential benefit is that ODR can enable the resolution of disputes where traditional courts have been unable to do so because of the complexity of applying foreign and international law. The final potential benefit is cost savings through quicker and more efficient resolution. Though this is again only speculative, it is based on the decreased costs of ODR as compared to traditional legal processes.

One of the potential benefits identified is that ODR can enable parties to resolve jurisdictional issues without either side making concessions on their legal position. This cannot be achieved in the traditional legal system where conceding on a jurisdictional issue would mean losing the entire case. If successful, this would result in a net transfer of legal authority and power from the current legal system to ODR processes.

The newness of ODR mechanisms in resolving jurisdictional issues means the potential benefits are only speculative at this stage. However, a joint research project between the Universities of Utrecht (Netherlands) and Massachusetts (US) is currently trying to chart the field of ODR and its potential use in conflict of laws and jurisdiction issues.

Jurisdiction, as a legal concept, is somewhat complex, but essentially it means the right to exercise authority. In the context of national legal systems, jurisdictional issues are quite complex and are usually only resolved once significant legal costs have been incurred. ODR has the potential to resolve many disputes incorporating jurisdictional issues at a fraction of the cost of traditional legal processes. Additionally, online Dispute Resolution (ODR) refers to a spectrum of processes and technologies designed to resolve disputes outside traditional courtroom settings, utilizing the internet and digital tools. From consumer disputes in e-commerce to complex commercial conflicts, ODR platforms offer tailored solutions to address diverse legal needs efficiently and effectively.

International Perspectives on ODR

Exploring international perspectives on Online Dispute Resolution (ODR) provides invaluable insights into its mechanisms, revealing a spectrum of approaches and challenges across different jurisdictions.

For instance, in the United States, platforms like eBay and Amazon have pioneered ODR systems to efficiently resolve disputes between buyers and sellers. These systems often involve automated negotiation and mediation processes, allowing parties to reach resolutions swiftly without resorting to costly litigation.

In contrast, the European Union has implemented ODR platforms such as the European Online Dispute Resolution (ODR) platform, designed to facilitate the resolution of disputes arising from online transactions within the EU.

This centralized platform enables consumers and businesses to resolve disputes through an online interface, enhancing access to justice and fostering cross-border commerce within the EU's single market. Additionally, countries like India have integrated ODR mechanisms into their legal framework to alleviate the burden on traditional courts and expedite dispute resolution. For instance, the Indian government launched the Digital India initiative, promoting the use of technology for resolving disputes through platforms like the ODR portal. These examples illustrate the diverse applications and benefits of ODR on an international scale, highlighting its potential to streamline dispute resolution processes, enhance access to justice, and foster trust in online transactions across borders [7].

Uzbekistan's Foray into ODR

Uzbekistan, amidst its ongoing legal reforms, has embraced the potential of ODR in enhancing access to justice and modernizing its dispute resolution mechanisms. The country's efforts to integrate technology into its legal infrastructure are exemplified by initiatives such as the "Single Portal of Interactive Public Services" (my.gov.uz), which serves as a centralized platform for online dispute resolution in administrative and civil matters. Through this portal, litigants can initiate complaints, engage in mediation, and receive adjudication electronically, bypassing traditional bureaucratic hurdles. Furthermore, legislative reforms, including the enactment of the Law on Mediation, provide a robust legal framework for ODR implementation in Uzbekistan, encompassing provisions for online mediation services. Furthermore, Uzbekistan's accession to the United Nations Convention on International Settlement Agreements Resulting from Mediation (the Singapore Convention) underscores its commitment to fostering ODR on a global scale.

Comparative Analysis and Challenges:

The United States stands as a trailblazer in ODR innovation, particularly in the realm of e-commerce disputes. Major platforms like eBay and PayPal have integrated automated ODR systems to efficiently resolve conflicts between buyers and sellers, streamlining the resolution process and minimizing legal costs. Additionally, institutions such as the American Arbitration Association (AAA) offer online arbitration services, contributing to the proliferation of ODR in commercial contexts.

Regardingly, within the European Union, ODR mechanisms have gained traction through initiatives like the European ODR platform. This platform aims to facilitate the resolution of disputes arising from online transactions, providing consumers and businesses with accessible avenues for mediation or arbitration. By fostering cross-border commerce while safeguarding consumer rights, the EU's ODR framework serves as a model for regulatory convergence in the digital age. Furthermore, Singapore has emerged as a global leader in ODR, leveraging technology to bolster its reputation as a hub for international arbitration. The Singapore International Mediation Centre (SIMC) offers cutting-edge online mediation services, catering to parties embroiled in commercial disputes worldwide. Singapore's proactive approach to ODR, coupled with its robust legal framework and technological infrastructure, has positioned it as a frontrunner in the global dispute resolution landscape. While Uzbekistan's strides towards embracing ODR are commendable, disparities persist concerning technological infrastructure, legal frameworks, and cultural acceptance compared to international counterparts. Challenges such as digital literacy, privacy concerns, and enforcement mechanisms necessitate careful consideration in Uzbekistan's quest to harness the full potential of ODR.

The evolution of Online Dispute Resolution (ODR) signifies a monumental transformation in the dispensation of justice, heralding a departure from conventional legal norms and spanning across geographical divides. In Uzbekistan, the country's proactive efforts to incorporate ODR into its legal framework reflect a profound commitment to embracing innovation and advancing modernization within its judicial system.

By leveraging lessons gleaned from global practices and taking into account the unique nuances of its legal jurisdiction, Uzbekistan has the opportunity to refine its ODR infrastructure to guarantee fair and inclusive access to justice for its diverse populace. Beyond Uzbekistan's borders, ODR has emerged as a vital instrument for resolving disputes efficiently and affordably, particularly in the realm of international commerce and cross-border transactions.

Platforms like eBay and Amazon have demonstrated the efficacy of ODR in facilitating timely resolutions between parties situated across different jurisdictions, streamlining processes, and alleviating the burden on conventional court systems. In light of these developments, the integration of ODR into Uzbekistan's legal fabric not only exemplifies the country's commitment to judicial reform but also positions it at the forefront of leveraging technological innovations to enhance access to justice and promote equitable resolution of disputes, both domestically and internationally.

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